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Research Article

**THE ROLE OF ORGANIZATIONAL HEALTH AND
PSYCHOLOGICAL HARDINESS IN PREDICTING JOB
SATISFACTION AMONG EMPLOYEES OF SPECIAL
ECONOMIC ZONE OF SHIRAZ**Seyed Afshin Hashemi¹ and Dr. Seyed Ahmad Mirjafari^{2*}¹ Department of Psychology, Arsanjan Branch, Islamic Azad University, Arsanjan Iran² Assistant Professor, Department of Psychology, Arsanjan Branch, Islamic Azad University, Arsanjan Iran**Abstract:**

To investigate the predictive role of organizational health (OH) and hardiness in job satisfaction of Shiraz Special Economic Zone personals. The statistical population consisted of all employees of the special economic zone of Shiraz, whose number was 270 people this year. An available sample of 159 based on Gerjcie- Morgan (1970) table, voluntarily answered Ahwaz hardiness inventory (AHI), Hoy et al. OH questionnaire and JDI. Data were analyzed using Pearson correlation coefficient and multiple regression. Results showed significant positive correlation between AHI, all components of OH, Expect institutional uniqueness with JDI. Regression analyzed indicated that hardiness and only academic emphasis and consideration components of OH were predictive job satisfaction, with academic emphasis having the highest and consideration the lowest role in this regard. Findings were discussed in high of previous research, their implication was presented and suggestions for further research were proposed.

Keywords: *hardiness, organizational health, job satisfaction***Corresponding author:**

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INTRODUCTION:

Organizations are now under the influence of factors such as increasing global competition, sudden changes, the need for quality and after-sales services, the availability of limited resources and ... under a lot of pressure, so if an organization wants to lead its business and economy, and in the field Competition should not be left out, it must have a highly professional, creative and motivated human resource. Of the indicators of the measure of the superiority of organizations in relation to each other, there are employees in those organizations whose loyalty, in particular their job satisfaction, enables them to perform the tasks performed in a higher quality and enhance the organization's performance, efficiency and effectiveness. Of the indicators of the measure of the superiority of organizations in relation to each other, there are employees in those organizations whose loyalty, in particular their job satisfaction, enables them to perform the tasks performed in a higher quality and enhance the organization's performance, efficiency and effectiveness. Job Satisfaction is an individual attitude toward the job and indicates the extent to which people are satisfied with their job and have a positive attitude towards it and consider it as the main axis of their lives. Job Satisfaction is one of the important factors in job success, which increases productivity, creativity and individual satisfaction, but job dissatisfaction leads to a reduction in performance and a lot of mistakes in employees. Therefore, managers in different ways are looking to increase their employees' job satisfaction. The administrative system, especially human capital, plays a very important role in the development of the country and can accelerate the process of development of the country in terms of justice and provide a healthy, clean and agile system (Nick Pey et al., 2015). A group of people believe job satisfaction is heavily influenced by psychological factors. In other words, these individuals consider job satisfaction primarily from a psychological point of view. They consider it as a psychological factor and they consider job satisfaction as a kind of emotional adjustment to the job and employment conditions. That is, if the desired job provides the desired pleasure to the person, then the person is happy with his job. In contrast, if the desired job does not give pleasure and satisfaction to the person, then the individual is looking for a change in his job (Karimifar, 2001). According to Hapak (1935), job satisfaction is a complex and multidimensional concept associated with psychological, physical and social factors. Only one factor does not cause job satisfaction, but a certain combination of factors leads to the person who is employed at a certain moment of time satisfied with his job (quoted from Shafiabadi,

2002). By controlling some of the variables, researchers concluded that high hardiness leads to a low disease and a low tolerance to high disease. This finding was both true in the short run and in the long run, it was also found in the study that the impact of persistence on maintaining and maintaining health is particularly evident when stress is intense and at a high level (Haghighi et al., 2011). The concept of organizational health is a unique concept that allows us to have a great image of the organization's health. In healthy organizations, employees are committed and committed, and have high morale and high performance (Jahed, 2005).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

This research is descriptive and correlational, which is designed and evaluated to evaluate the role of organizational health and psychological hardiness in predicting job satisfaction among employees of special economic zone of Shiraz.

Statistical population, sample and sampling method

The statistical population of this study included all employees of special economic zone of Shiraz city in total 270 people.

Sample and method of sampling: After determining the statistical population, the sample of this study was 159 employees (95 males and 64 females) based on the sample size of Gerjesi and Morgan (1970) Available to completed questionnaires.

Table 1: Distribution of respondents by sex

Percent	Abundance		
59.7	95	Man	sex
40.3	64	Female	
100	159	Total	

Research tools

1- Hardiness questionnaire in Ahvaz

Ahvaz Hardiness Inventory is a paper self-sampling scale that has 27 materials. This scale was developed by factor analysis by Keyamarci, Najarian, Mehrabizadeh Honarmand (1998).

2- Job Discription Inventory

The Job Satisfaction Questionnaire, which was standardized by visoki & Korum in 1991, includes 39 questions or items that include 5 indicators (type of work, supervisor, co-workers, promotion and promotion, and salaries and benefits).

3. Organizational Health Questionnaire:

This questionnaire was first prepared by Hoy et al. (OHI) (1996).

Data analysis method

In this study, the data were extracted and analyzed using descriptive statistics and inferential statistics. For analyzing the data obtained in the first and second hypotheses, multiple regression tests were used in SPSS software (version 22).

Standard deviation	Average	Maximum score	Minimum score	Abundance	
13.871	140.01	177	91	159	Organizational Health - Total Score
3.941	23.04	32	9	159	Dimensions 1 Institutional Unity
2.932	17.42	25	11	159	Dimensions 2 Administrator Influence
3.395	14.38	24	5	159	Dimensions 3 Noteworthy
4.088	17.77	25	5	159	Dimensions 4 Construction
3.141	15.26	25	7	159	Dimensions 5 Resource support
4.205	28.14	41	19	159	Dimensions 6 Morale
4.437	23.99	35	12	159	Dimensions 7 Scientific emphasis
11.091	48.83	69	22	159	Psychological Hardiness - Total Score
19.178	119.67	167	68	159	Job Satisfaction - Total Score
				159	Total

Table 3: Correlation matrix of zero-time relation between research variables

10	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1		
									1	r	Organizational Health - Total Score
								1	-.007	r	Dimensions 1 Institutional Unity
							1	.087	.490**	r	Dimensions 2 Administrator Influence
						1	-.037	.100	.610**	r	Dimensions 3 Noteworthy
					1	.400**	.303**	-.198*	.662**	r	Dimensions 4 Construction
				1	.215**	.231**	.221**	-.203*	.585**	r	Dimensions 5 Resource support
			1	.389**	.381**	.381**	.340**	-.348**	.743**	r	Dimensions 6 Morale
		1	.540**	.411**	.303**	.185*	.066	-.389**	.615**	r	Dimensions 7 Scientific emphasis
	1	.267**	.237**	.049	.141	-.265**	.427**	-.280**	.156*	r	Psychological Hardiness - Total Score
1	.257**	.530**	.396**	.361**	.238**	.261**	.085	-.276**	.445**	r	Job Satisfaction - Total Score

: *Significance level is less than 0.05 ; ** 0Significance level is less than 0.01 .0

Sample number: 159 people

Inferential Findings of the Research

Analysis of research hypotheses:

Hypothesis 1: Organizational health is able to predict part of the variance in employee job satisfaction.

In order to investigate the effect of the predictor variable on the criterion variable, based on this

hypothesis, the multi-variable regression method was used in a concurrent manner, the results of which are shown in the following tables.

Table 4: Model summary, variance level of variance of job satisfaction by organizational health dimensions in general

Estimate the standard error	Adjusted coefficient of determination	coefficient of determination	Correlation	Model
15.966	.307	.338	.581	1

Table 5: Analysis of variance using nave test between organizational health dimensions and job satisfaction

significance level	F	average of squares	Degrees of freedom	sum of squares	Model	
.001	10.994	2802.745	7	19619.216	regression	1
		254.926	151	38493.778	The remainder	
			158	58112.994	Total	

Table 6: Model summary, variance level of variance of job satisfaction by psychological hardiness

Estimate the standard error	Adjusted coefficient of determination	coefficient of determination	Correlation	Model
18.592	.060	.066	.257	1

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION:

On Research Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: Organizational health is able to predict part of the variance in employee job satisfaction. The results

Table 7: Analysis of variance using ANOVA test between psychological hardiness and job satisfaction

significance level	F	average of squares	Degrees of freedom	sum of squares	Model	
.001	11.115	3842.144	1	3842.144	regression	1
		345.674	157	54270.850	The remainder	
			158	58112.994	Total	

showed that, at 0.307 The %31 variance of job satisfaction variance was explained by organizational health dimensions and the result of variance analysis was significantly less than 0.01 Has been meaningful to be 0.001. Also, considering the amount of regression coefficients in the column (beta), among the dimensions of organizational health, the inclusion component for a standard deviation was %17 considering the significance level less than 0.05, there was a positive effect on the employee's job satisfaction variable and predicted it, and the scientific emphasis component for a standard deviation could be %39, According to the significance level of less than 0.01, has a positive effect on the job satisfaction variable and therefore it is concluded that the component of scientific emphasis on the stronger predictor component for job satisfaction The staff has been. This research is in line with researches such as: Nick Pey and colleagues (2015), Ali Nejad et al. (2015), Hosseini Hafashejani et al (2015), Maleki et al (2012), Aram (2010), Saedi (2010), Results Study of Fitnes, (2003), French and Kaplan (1973).

Hypothesis 2: Psychological hardiness can predict part of the variance in employee job satisfaction.

The results showed that, at 0.066 the %6.6 variance of job satisfaction variance was explained by psychological hardiness and the result of variance analysis was significantly less than 0.01 Has a meaningful value of 0.001. Regarding the regression coefficient indicated in the column (Beta), the

psychological hardiness variable for a standard deviation is capable of %26 considering the significance level less than 0.01, there is a positive effect on the employee's job satisfaction variable and predict it. Therefore, it is concluded that psychological hardiness has predicted the job satisfaction of the employees. This research is in line with researches such as Asadi et al. (2015), Farhangi et al (2014), Safari (2014), Erfaninia (2013), Madi (1987).

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